

Histopathological Examination of Non-Neoplastic Anomalies in Cervical Lymphatic Tissues

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Abstract:

Cervical lymphadenopathy remains one of the most frequently observed clinical presentations, with an increasing incidence of non-neoplastic lymph node disorders. This study focuses on our observations over a one-year period at a tertiary care hospital in Gujrat. While fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is commonly employed as the initial diagnostic tool due to its accessibility and efficiency, it has certain limitations in its diagnostic accuracy. For more definitive diagnosis, particularly in cases where FNAC may be inconclusive, excision biopsy followed by a detailed histopathological examination remains the gold standard in evaluating cervical lymphadenopathy.

Keywords: Cervical lymphadenopathy; Histopathological examination.

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Introduction

Lymphadenopathy refers to an abnormal enlargement or alteration in the characteristics of lymph nodes, resulting from a wide spectrum of disease processes. These can be broadly classified into categories such as malignancies, infections, autoimmune disorders, miscellaneous conditions, unusual cases, and iatrogenic causes.

Among all forms of lymphadenopathy, head and neck lymphadenopathy accounts for approximately 55% of cases and holds significant clinical relevance as it is often detected early during medical evaluations [1].

The most common cause of lymphadenopathy, particularly in children, is benign and frequently stems from infections, especially those with viral origins. When lymph node enlargement is confined to the cervical region, it is termed cervical lymphadenopathy, which is more frequently associated with non-neoplastic conditions than with malignant processes.

The gold standard for investigating cervical lymphadenopathy remains histopathological examination, providing a definitive diagnosis in such cases [2-4]. The non-malignant causes of lymphadenopathy are numerous and diverse, encompassing a wide array of conditions.

Infections such as tuberculosis, brucellosis, mononucleosis syndromes, and cat scratch disease are some of the primary causes. Additionally,

connective tissue disorders like systemic lupus erythematosus and rheumatoid arthritis can also lead to lymphadenopathy.

There are also iatrogenic causes, where certain medications, including phenytoin, carbamazepine, captopril, allopurinol, and atenolol, trigger the enlargement of lymph nodes [5].

In patients presenting with peripheral lymphadenopathy, an excision biopsy of the most accessible lymph node is crucial for establishing an early diagnosis. This procedure provides vital material for histopathological analysis, which is key to determining the underlying cause and guiding patient management [6, 7].

However, in a considerable number of cases, the cause of lymphadenopathy remains elusive. This study was conducted with the objective of examining the histopathological spectrum of non-neoplastic lesions found in cervical lymph node biopsies within this region.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective study was conducted in the Department of Pathology at Swaminarayan Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, a tertiary-level hospital located in Kalol, Ahmedabad, over the course of one year.

Clinical data and histopathological slides from non-neoplastic cervical lymph node biopsies were

collected and analysed for inclusion in the study. A total of 80 patients underwent cervical lymph node biopsy to confirm their diagnosis.

Results

In this study of 60 cases, 35 patients (58%) were female, and 25 patients (41%) were male, resulting in a male-to-female ratio of 1:1.4, indicating a higher

prevalence among females. The majority of patients fell within the 21-30 age group (as shown in Table 1). In this study, a diverse range of cases was observed, with tuberculous lymphadenitis being the most common diagnosis, followed by non-specific lymphadenitis (as shown in Table 2).

Table 1: Age wise Distribution of Non-neoplastic lesions cervical lymph Nodes

Age	Non-Neoplastic lesions	Percentage
<10	3	5
11-20	11	18.33
21-30	18	30
31-40	14	23.33
41-50	10	16.67
51-60	2	3.33
61-70	1	1.67
>71	1	1.67
Total	60	100

Table 2: Incidence of Non-Neoplastic Lesions of Cervical Lymph Nodes

Name of Lesion	No. of Cases	Percentage
Tuberculous Lymphadenitis	30	50
Chronic Nonspecific Lymphadenitis	20	33.33
Kikuchi Lymphadenopathy	8	13.33
Kimura Lymphadenopathy	2	3.33

Discussion

The enlargement of lymph nodes or lymphadenitis can result from the proliferation of cells in the lymphocyte and monocyte-macrophage system in response to antigenic stimuli, or from the infiltration of inflammatory cells due to infections affecting the lymph nodes. According to Chabra et al.[1], more than two-thirds of patients with lymphadenopathy in primary care have non-specific causes, often related to upper respiratory infections (viral or bacterial), while less than 1% have malignancies.

In this study, we observed a predominance of female patients, with a male-to-female ratio of 1:1.4. Similar findings were reported by Rehman et al. and Vemulapalli N.K. et al. [8, 9] However, Paliwal U.K. et al. [10] noted a slightly higher male predominance. The majority of patients in this study were between the ages of 21-30, consistent with the findings of Rehman et al. Conversely, Paliwal U.K. et al. [10] and Vemulapalli N.K. et al.[9] identified the first and second decades of life as the most common age groups in their respective studies.

In our study, tuberculous lymphadenitis was the most frequently encountered lesion, with 36 cases (46%). This observation closely aligns with Rehman A. et al. [8], who reported a 50.61% incidence of tuberculous lymphadenitis, and Vemulapalli N.K. et al. [9], who reported 68%. Similar incidences of tuberculosis have been reported by various authors [11, 12]. In contrast, Moor J.W. et al. [13] reported

that chronic nonspecific lymphadenopathy was the most prevalent cause, with an incidence of 50.83%.

In our study, non-specific lymphadenitis was the second most common cause of lymphadenopathy, comparable to the findings of Roy et al. [14] in South India. In the United States, non-specific reactive hyperplasia is one of the most common causes of lymphadenopathy, accounting for nearly half of all cases [15, 16].

We identified eight cases (8%) of Kikuchi lymphadenopathy in this study. This finding is closely aligned with the reports by Moor J.W. et al. (4.16%) and Rehman A. et al. (3.70%). Additionally, we observed two cases (2.5%) of toxoplasma lymphadenitis, which is comparable to the 1.66% incidence reported by Moor J.W. et al., though other studies did not report any cases of toxoplasma lymphadenitis.

In our study, we also encountered rare cases of Kimura lymphadenopathy and sinus histiocytosis with massive lymphadenopathy, both representing 2% of the total cases. Furthermore, Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) lymphadenitis, Castleman lymphadenopathy, and dermatopathic lymphadenopathy were each reported in 1.2% of cases. These specific lesions were not noted in other studies. However, other conditions found in previous studies, such as sarcoidosis, systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), foreign body reaction, and cat scratch lymphadenitis, were not observed in the current study [17-20].

Conclusion

Cervical lymphadenopathy is one of the most common clinical presentations in patients visiting both outpatient and inpatient departments. The underlying causes of cervical lymphadenopathy are diverse, ranging from viral and microbial infections to inflammatory and malignant conditions. While fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is typically the first-line investigation, histopathological examination remains the "gold standard" for providing a comprehensive diagnosis. In conclusion, this study identified various non-neoplastic lesions in cervical lymph node biopsy specimens. Biopsy plays a crucial role in the effective management of non-neoplastic cervical lymph node diseases, offering valuable insights for accurate diagnosis and treatment planning.

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